

Optimizing Speed Frame Drafting Variables for Yarn Uniformity and Hairiness Using Taguchi Design

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Abstract:

Background: The drafting system configuration in speed frames significantly influences the quality of spun yarn. Factors such as yarn irregularity, coefficient of variation (CV %), imperfections, and hairiness are crucial parameters for evaluating yarn quality. This study compares the performance of PK 1500 and PK 1600 drafting systems with 3-over-3 and 4-over-4 configurations using Taguchi methods to optimize drafting variables for better yarn uniformity and reduced hairiness.

Methodology: The study analyzed the effects of front and back top roller pressure, spacer size, and overhang in the drafting region for PK 1500 (3/3 and 4/4) and PK 1600 (4/4) systems. Taguchi design and analysis of variance (ANOVA) were employed to evaluate the impact of these variables on yarn properties, including irregularity, CV%, imperfections, and hairiness.

Results: The 3-over-3 configuration of the PK 1500 drafting system outperformed the 4-over-4 setups in producing yarn with lower unevenness, reduced CV%, and fewer imperfections. Additionally, the hairiness was found to be significantly higher in yarns produced with the 4-over-4 configurations of both PK 1500 and PK 1600 systems.

Conclusion: The study concluded that the 3-over-3 drafting system in the PK 1500 configuration offers superior yarn quality for the tested material and machine settings. This configuration is recommended for achieving optimal yarn uniformity and minimized hairiness, highlighting its advantages over 4-over-4 setups.

Keywords: Drafting system, PK 1500 3/3, PK 1500 4/4, PK 1600 4/4, Taguchi method

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1. Introduction

Draft limits inhibit the direct feeding of drawn slivers to ring frames machine. A two-step reduction method is essential for producing high-quality yarn. Speed frames, succeeding draw frames, impart twist and diminish weight while maintaining sliver integrity but sometime roving preparation adversely affects spinning performance. Now a days, new ring frames can accommodate higher-draft speed frame material for coarser hanks, hence enhancing the output of the machine [1]. Further, enhancing speed frame operation within a designated timeframe is essential for the effective production of high-quality roving. While many studies have concentrated on enhancing yarn quality by modifying fibre parameters and spinning machines parameters in the spinning line [2-4], there are few investigations that emphasize improving yarn quality through the optimization of speed frame drafting parameters using the Taguchi method [5]. This study seeks to optimize the parameters of the speed frame drafting system (front/back top roller pressure, spacer size, and overhang) via the Taguchi method to improve yarn quality in the conventional ring spinning system.

2 Materials and Method

2.1 Preparation of samples

As illustrated in Table 1, samples were prepared using Sankar-6 cotton with an L9 mixed orthogonal array, based on Taguchi's experimental design. The design was developed using the statistical software Minitab® 17, with the

specifics and responses detailed in Table 2. Initially, the process parameters of the roving frame, which is equipped with a PK-1500 3/3 drafting system, were optimized using the Taguchi method in the orthogonal array L9. These parameters include front top roller pressure, rear top roller pressure, spacer size, and overhang. To eliminate any potential influence of machine conditions on the experimental outcomes, ten finisher draw frame cans were collected from the same machine and processed onto the same set of spindles. Apart from the variables under study, all other parameters were maintained consistently across the spindles. A total of nine samples, each with a unique combination of variables, were spun, and ten bobbins were prepared for each combination. The procedure was repeated for the PK-1500 4/4 and PK-1600 4/4 drafting systems, resulting in 27 (9 x 3) distinct roving frame samples, each prepared using one of the three drafting systems. The drafting system setting used on different drafting system at speed frame are shown in Table 3. These samples were then creeled onto the same set of spindles on the ring frame to assess the impact of the different drafting systems on cotton Lycra yarn. The 30s Ne core yarns are produced on a ring frame by feeding Lycra filament yarn through the front roller nip and roving through the drafting zone of the ring frame. The spindle speed and other parameters of the spinning process were constant during all yarn manufacturing procedures (Spindle speed-14000 rpm; Break draft-1.21; Main draft-35.4; Spacer-2.25 mm).

Taguchi's experimental design was employed to generate textile samples and analyse the impact of each controllable factor on multiple responses, including yarn irregularity, CV%, imperfections, and hairiness. The study considered controllable variables such as front top roller pressure, rear top roller pressure, overhang, and spacer size. The yarn hairiness, irregularity and imperfections were evaluated using an Uster Evenness Tester (UT-6).

Table 1 - L9 orthogonal array

Run	Overhang	Front top roller pressure	Back top roller pressure	Spacer size
1	1	1	1	1
2	1	2	2	2
3	1	3	3	3
4	2	1	2	3
5	2	2	3	1
6	2	3	1	2
7	3	1	3	2
8	3	2	1	3
9	3	3	2	1

Table 2 - Actual values of the process parameters of drafting system of speed frame corresponding to coded levels

Actual values				
PK 1500 3/3				
Coded levels	Front top roller pressure	Back top roller pressure	Overhang	Spacer size
1	20	15	2	4.7
2	25	20	4	5.1
3	30	25	6	8.9
PK 1500 4/4				
Coded levels	Front top roller pressure	Back top roller pressure	Overhang	Spacer size
1	20	15	2	4.7
2	25	20	4	5.1
3	30	25	6	8.9
PK 1600 4/4				
Coded levels	Front top roller pressure	Back top roller pressure	Overhang	Spacer size

1	20	10	2	4.7
2	25	15	4	5.1
3	30	20	6	8.9

Table 3- Drafting system setting in Speed frame

	PK-1500 3/3	PK-1500 4/4	PK-1600 4/4
Main Draft zone, mm	40	45	45
Break Draft zone, mm	50	55	55
Top Roller diameter, mm	28/25/28	28/25/28/28	28/25/28/28
Bottom Roller diameter, mm	30/27/30	30/28/30/30	30/28/30/30
Total draft	10.1	10.1	10.1
Break draft	1.17	1.15	1.15
Main draft	8.60	8.78	8.78

Table 4 - Experiment layout using L9 orthogonal array for individual drafting system and with their responses

Expt No	Drafting System	Overhang	Front Roller Pressure	Back Roller Pressure	Spacer Size	U %	CVm %	IPI Values	Hairiness index	S3u /100m	S1+2u /100m
P 1	PK-1500 3/3	6	20(BLACK)	25(RED)	5.1	9.25	12.82	97	5.78	3796	13165
P 2		6	25(GREEN)	15(BLACK)	8.9	9.35	12.23	41	5.95	3961	13308
P 3		6	30(RED)	20(GREEN)	4.7	9.45	11.73	45	5.89	3851	13188
P 4		4	20(BLACK)	20(GREEN)	8.9	9.28	12.01	45	5.98	3496	13135
P 5		4	25(GREEN)	25(RED)	4.7	9.33	11.83	47	6.01	3815	13163
P 6		4	30(RED)	15(BLACK)	5.1	9.49	11.62	53	6.04	3127	12922
P 7		2	20(BLACK)	15(BLACK)	4.7	9.15	11.75	35	6.15	3807	13560
P 8		2	25(GREEN)	20(GREEN)	5.1	9.63	11.61	57	5.78	3767	12655
P 9		2	30(RED)	25(RED)	8.9	9.41	12.16	50	6.89	3553	12313
S 1	PK-1500 4/4	6	20(BLACK)	25(RED)	5.1	9.75	12.46	100	5.12	2496	12,165
S 2		6	25(GREEN)	15(BLACK)	8.9	9.45	11.94	52	5.15	2561	12,308
S 3		6	30(RED)	20(GREEN)	4.7	9.55	12.10	57	5.18	2551	12,388
S 4		4	20(BLACK)	20(GREEN)	8.9	9.48	11.96	45	4.96	2496	12,165
S 5		4	25(GREEN)	25(RED)	4.7	9.63	12.23	85	5.18	2315	12,063
S 6		4	30(RED)	15(BLACK)	5.1	9.79	12.39	75	5.15	2527	12,922
S 7		2	20(BLACK)	15(BLACK)	4.7	9.55	12.05	59	5.28	2807	13,860
S 8		2	25(GREEN)	20(GREEN)	5.1	9.83	12.50	89	5.16	2667	12,655
S 9		2	30(RED)	25(RED)	8.9	9.61	12.41	85	4.45	2153	12,313
R 1	PK-1600 4/4	6	20(BLACK)	20(RED)	5.1	9.79	12.37	65	4.99	2451	12,135
R 2		6	25(GREEN)	10(BLACK)	8.9	9.68	12.31	79	4.96	2458	12,528
R 3		6	30(RED)	15(GREEN)	4.7	9.58	12.40	97	4.89	2441	12,145
R 4		4	20(BLACK)	15(GREEN)	8.9	9.46	12.03	80	5.04	2543	12,554
R 5		4	25(GREEN)	20(RED)	4.7	9.71	12.22	98	4.93	2458	12,143
R 6		4	30(RED)	10(BLACK)	5.1	9.53	12.22	63	5.02	2544	12,280
R 7		2	20(BLACK)	10(BLACK)	4.7	9.57	12.06	86	5.07	2745	12,286
R 8		2	25(GREEN)	15(GREEN)	5.1	9.72	12.30	71	5.18	2560	12,470
R 9		2	30(RED)	20(RED)	8.9	9.66	12.21	74	4.97	2946	12,577

2.2 Taguchi method

The Taguchi method is a methodology employed to reduce variability in a process through the creation of rigorous tests. The primary objective of this strategy is to produce a high-quality product while minimising production costs. The Taguchi method was formulated by Dr. Genichi Taguchi from Japan. He asserted that diversity is crucial to contemplate. Taguchi devised a methodology for experimental design to examine the influence of numerous parameters on the mean and variability of a process performance characteristic, which assesses the efficacy of the process. The Taguchi method employs orthogonal arrays to reduce variance and optimize process parameters. In the Taguchi method, the signal to noise (S/N) ratio is used as a performance characteristic to measure process robustness and to evaluate deviation from desired values [6]. The S/N ratio, a logarithmic function, is computed by assessing the proportion of signal (mean) to the noise (standard deviation) [7]. There exist three types of S/N ratios, namely, higher-the-better (S/N)_{HTB}, nominal-the-best(S/N)_{NTB} and smaller-the-better(S/N)_{STB}.

The actual values of maximum S/N ratio were also evaluated directly from the curves of S/N ratio with change in process variable by using the equation:

$$S/N_{\max} = S/N + (S/NA_{\max} - S/N) + (S/NB_{\max} - S/N) + (S/NC_{\max} - S/N) + (S/ND_{\max} - S/N) \quad (1)$$

where S/N_{\max} is maximum actual value from the graph; S/N , overall average value of the S/N ratio; S/NA_{\max} , maximum value of S/N ratio in plot of Overhang, S/NB_{\max} , maximum value of S/N ratio in plot of Front roller pressure, S/NC_{\max} maximum value of S/N ratio in plot of Back roller pressure and S/ND_{\max} maximum value a S/N ratio in plot of Spacer size.

3. Result and Discussion

Table 4 presents the average values of yarn irregularity, coefficient of variation (CV%), imperfections, and hairiness for yarns produced from roving using PK 1500 3/3, PK 1500 4/4, and PK 1600 4/4 drafting systems while maintaining nine sets of process variables. The actual values of signal-to-noise (S/N) ratios within the 95% confidence limits (S/NL and S/NH) for the various drafting parameters investigated are also provided in Tables 6 and 7.

The influence of four experimental factors, i.e., overhangs, front roller pressure, back roller pressure on yarn characteristics for different drafting systems was evaluated for significance using analysis of variance (ANOVA) at a 95% level of significance (Table 5).

3.1 Irregularity

Table 5 presents the ANOVA results for different variables of the speed frame drafting system on yarn irregularity. The results indicate that the drafting system and spacer size have a significant effect on yarn irregularity, while other variables like front roller pressure, back roller pressure, and overhang do not significantly affect it. As can be seen from Table 6, the yarn spun using the PK 1500 3/3 drafting system exhibits the lowest average irregularity, followed by PK 1500 4/4 and PK 1600 4/4. This is attributed to the narrower roller setting of PK 1500 3/3, which offers better control of shorter and less cohesive fibers in the primary drafting zone. Wider roller settings led to increased yarn irregularity due to greater fiber floating between the rollers [8]. Furthermore, the marginal R^2 values for all systems indicate that front top roller pressure, back top roller pressure, overhang, and spacer size have negligible effects on yarn irregularity (Table 8). However, the front top roller pressure is the most significant factor affecting yarn irregularity in the case of PK 1500 3/3. Figure 1 depicts the S/N ratio plot of yarn irregularity for various process variables. A lower S/N ratio indicates a superior condition. The initial increase in top roller pressure narrows the gap between the pressure fields of the middle and front rollers, improving fiber management and reducing yarn irregularity [9]. However, further increases in top roller pressure can lead to overlapping friction fields, hindering fiber movement and increasing yarn irregularity [10]. The optimal values of variables for yarn irregularity in various speed frame drafting systems, along with their corresponding MINITAB-predicted means, are presented in Table 6.

Table 5 - ANNOVA test results

P-value						
	Uster,	CVm%	IPI	Hairiness Index	S3u/100m	S1+2u/100m
Drafting System	0.00^s	0.065	0.009^s	0.00^s	0.00^s	0.005^s
Overhang	0.617	0.225	0.835	0.712	0.192	0.652
Front roller pressure	0.072	0.944	0.959	0.989	0.529	0.450
Back Roller Pressure	0.412	0.10	0.098	0.846	0.825	0.084
Spacer Size	0.01^s	0.219	0.24	0.957	0.633	0.584
R²	0.788	0.537	0.572	0.823	0.917	0.608
S= significant at 95% confidence limit						

Table 6 - Optimum values of process variables of drafting systems of speed frame for individual properties with their predicted mean

		Overhang (mm)	Front roller pressure (dAN)	Back roller Pressure (dAN)	Spacer size (mm)	Predicted mean	S/N ratio	
P	K	U%	6	20	25	4.7	09.11	-19.19

Taguchi rank	2	4	1	1	1	2	4	3	1
% V Effect	0.80	9.96	5.33	31.81	13.15	15.70	4.65	8.22	2.99
R ²	48.74	69.03	48.79	48.43	54.75	60.42	42.20	66.54	3.14

Figure 1 - S/N ratio plot of U% with change in process variables

3.2 CVm%

The ANOVA results in Table 5 show that the drafting system of the speed frame has no substantial impact on the yarn CVm%. However, the yarn spun using the PK 1500 3/3 drafting system exhibits the lowest average CVm%, followed by PK 1500 4/4 and PK 1600 4/4 (Table 6). This is attributed to the optimal main and break drafts provided by a 3-over-3 roller drafting system, which minimizes CVm%. Conversely, the wider roller spacing and uneven draft distribution in 4-over-4 systems increase CVm% [11, 12]. Table 8 quantifies the relative importance of various variables on CVm% for three speed frame drafting systems. Marginal R² values indicate that front top roller pressure, back top roller pressure, overhang, and spacer size have negligible effects on CVm% for PK1500 4/4 and PK1600 4/4. However, for PK 1500 3/3, overhang (22.0) and back top roller pressure (20.24) significantly influence yarn irregularity, while front top roller pressure (15.83) and spacer size (9.96) have minor impacts.

The S/N ratio plot in Figure 2 illustrates the relationship between process variables and CVm% for the speed frame drafting system. For PK 1500 3/3, CVm% increases with overhang due to compromised fiber control caused by the increased distance between the roller nip line and the aprons' opening. The S/N ratio plot also shows that for PK 1500 3/3, CVm% initially decreases with increasing top roller load, then increases to a threshold. The initial decrease is attributed to the narrowing of the pressure gradient between the front and middle rollers, improving fiber control. However, excessive top roller load can lead to overlapping friction fields, hindering fiber progression and increasing CVm%. Spacer size has a minimal impact on CVm%, as hook removal primarily depends on main draft and top roller pressure.

Figure 2 - S/N ratio plot of CV% with change in process variables

3.3 Imperfection

As can be seen from Table 7, the PK 1500 3/3 system exhibits the lowest average IPI values, followed by PK 1500 4/4 and PK 1600 4/4. This is attributed to the larger drafting area in 4 over 4 systems, allowing for better fiber entanglement and reduced slippage [12]. On the other hand, a low R^2 value for PK 1600 4/4 indicates a weak correlation between IPI and the individual variables (Table 8). Back top roller pressure has the greatest impact on IPI for PK 1500 3/3 and 4/4, while overhang and spacer size have lesser effects. The S/N ratio plot of IPI for various process variables (Figure 3) depict that both PK 1500 3/3 and PK 1500 4/4 drafting systems showed a decrease in IPI with increasing top roller loads. This is because inadequate pressure on the back roller causes improper drafted strand to emerge from the drafting zone and move in groups, leading to premature acceleration of shorter fibres during drafting, which, in turn, results in an increase in number of thick and thin places [13]. However, a further increase in top roller load alters the friction field, which facilitates the contact between the fibres in the strand, thereby reducing the rove irregularity, and consequently yarn imperfection [14]. The spacer size also has a significantly impact on yarn imperfections. Increasing spacer size in both PK 1500 3/3 and PK 1500 4/4 drafting systems results in lower IPI values. This could be attributed to changes in cohesive forces between fibers, leading to smoother attenuation and improved yarn structure.

Figure 3 - S/N ratio plot of IPI Values with change in process variables

3.4 Hairiness Index, S3u/100m and S1+2u/100m

Table 5 presents the ANOVA results of different speed frame drafting system variables on hairiness index, S3u/100m, and S1+2u/100m. The results indicate that the drafting system significantly influences all yarn hairiness values. However, four variables—front roller pressure, back roller pressure, overhang, and spacer size—do not significantly affect any hairiness value. The R^2 values of 0.823 for hairiness index and 0.917 for S3u/100m suggest that drafting system variables have a strong effect on these hairiness properties. The data reveals that the average values of hairiness and longer hairs (S3u/100m) are lowest for yarns spun from the PK 1500 4/4 drafting system, followed by PK 1600 4/4 and PK 1500 3/3 (Table 9). Conversely, the average values of shorter hairs (S2u/100m) are lowest for PK 1600 4/4, followed by PK 1500 4/4 and PK 1500 3/3. Overall, the 4/4 drafting system exhibits lower hairiness compared to the 3/3 drafting system. This might be due to the additional condensing zone in the 4/4 system, which condenses and integrates fibers into the roving structure, thereby reducing yarn hairiness. On the other hand, the weak average R^2 values for hairiness index, S3u/100m, and S1+2u/100m for PK 1500 3/3 indicate a weak correlation with overhang, front top roller pressure, and spacer size (Table 10). For PK 1500 4/4, overhang has the least impact on yarn hairiness index, while back top roller pressure and spacer size have significant impacts. In contrast, for PK 1600 4/4, overhang has the greatest influence on yarn hairiness index, while other factors have negligible effects. For S3u/100m, back top roller pressure has the greatest impact for PK 1500 4/4, while overhang has the greatest impact for PK 1600 4/4. Other factors have negligible effects. For S1+2u/100m, overhang has the greatest impact for both PK 1500 4/4 and PK 1600 4/4, while other factors have negligible effects. The S/N ratio plots of yarn hairiness verses speed frame drafting system variables (Figures 4-6) also show a reduction in hairiness values with increase in overhang due to a shortened spinning triangle. However, excessive overhang can lead to compromised fiber control and increased hairiness. Increasing spacer size also reduces hairiness by facilitating more uniform fiber attenuation and better incorporation into the roving structure [15].

Table 9 - S/N ratios and mean values of Hairiness Index, S3u/100m and S1+2u/100m of yarn

Smaller is better	PK 1500 3/3	PK 1500 4/4	PK 1600 4/4
Hairiness index			
S/N ratio calculated	-14.69	-12.97	-33.66
S/N ratio actual	-14.69	-12.96	-33.61
S/N L	-16.310	-13.250	-33.71
S/N H	-13.070	-12.670	-33.51
Average	6.05	5.07	5.01
Predicted	5.38	4.45	4.81
S3u/100m			
S/N ratio calculated	-66.4	-69.76	-70.31
S/N ratio actual	-66.4	-69.76	-70.32
S/N L	-67.14	-70.07	-70.58
S/N H	-65.66	-69.45	-70.06
Average	3685.889	2508	2571.778
Predicted	4023.33	3056.61	3259.67
S1+2u/100m			
S/N ratio calculated	-81.37	-82.11	-82.74
S/N ratio actual	-81.38	-82.10	-82.74
S/N L	-81.55	-82.23	-82.88
S/N H	-81.21	-81.99	-82.60
Average	13045.78	12537.44	12346.33
Predicted	12681	11739	11499.7

Table 10 - Changes in S/N ratio of yarn Hairiness Index, S3u/100m and S1+2u/100m as explained by ANOVA and ranked by the Taguchi method

	PK 1500 3/3			PK 1500 4/4			PK 1600 4/4		
	HI	S3u/100m	S1+2u/100m	HI	S3u/100m	S1+2u/100m	HI	S3u/100m	S1+2u/100m
Overhang									
Taguchi rank	2	4	1	4	4	1	1	1	1
% V Effect	26.56	3.75	0.26	10.71	0.02	22.89	41.05	58.99	48.15
Front top roller pressure									
Taguchi rank	3	1	4	3	2	4	3	2	3
% V Effect	15.27	39.85	4.66	11.48	18.98	7.87	13.76	2.68	0.02
Back top roller pressure									
Taguchi rank	4	3	2	2	1	2	4	4	2
% V Effect	5.38	1.17	0.33	23.52	51.00	7.38	7.28	0.85	11.99
Spacer Size									
Taguchi rank	1	2	3	1	3	3	2	3	4
% V Effect	22.56	16.23	8.43	44.35	17.22	2.60	0.85	11.17	0.06
R²	69.77	61.01	13.67	89.84	87.11	44.43	64.90	75.05	70.45

Figure 4- S/N ratio plot of Hairiness Index with change in Process Variables

Figure 5- S/N ratio plot of S3u/100m with change in Process Variables

Figure 6 - S/N ratio plot of S1+2u/100m with change in Process Variables

4. Conclusion

The roving produced by the 3-over-3 drafting system (PK 1500 3/3) exhibited improved unevenness, imperfection, and CVm% in comparison to the roving produced by the 4-over-4 drafting systems (PK 1500 4/4 and PK 1600 4/4). Additionally, the roving produced by the 4-over-4 drafting system (PK 1500 4/4 and PK 1600 4/4) had a higher level of yarn hairiness in comparison to the roving produced by the 3-over-3 drafting system. Moreover, the relatively low R² values for the various speed frame drafting systems and their variables suggest that yarn quality

is not significantly influenced by roving quality but may be primarily determined by specific parameters of the ring frame process.

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